

THE QUESTION OF DIVERSITY AS A FACTOR OF COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE IN ORGANIZATIONS

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Luciana Maria de Araújo Nascimento

Psychologist, lawyer and postgraduate in Applied Constitutional Law from Faculdade

Lagale.

Email: luci_anam_araujo@hotmail.com

ABSTRACT

The issue of human diversity is a theme that has been the target of several studies in several areas of human knowledge linked to human sciences such as psychology, sociology, and social psychology. One of the reasons why the issue of diversity is so fashionable is related to the struggles of minorities for more inclusion in society. These are minorities stigmatized for not fitting into the standards considered normal by society, such as people with disabilities and homosexuals, bisexuals, and LGBTQIA+. There is also the issue of racial prejudice that causes black people to be left out of the job market, or even if they have access to jobs, they cannot get the same opportunities as white people. The purpose of this article is to talk about the issue of minority inclusion as a factor of competitive advantage in organizations. Companies should reflect the society where there are the most diverse types of people: black people, disabled people, homosexuals, etc. Including all people is advantageous for companies as it makes them reflect the society where they are inserted and not artificial environments with handpicked people based on a standard of normativity that does not really reflect society. From diversity arise innovative solutions that can leverage an organization's business.

Keywords: Diversity, competitive advantage, inclusion.

1. INTRODUCTION

As we have already stated, the issue of diversity is on the agenda of all spheres of society and several groups have been engaged in the sense of expanding this discussion in order to give the so-called minorities the same opportunities as other people in society, whether in the area of education, culture, work, etc. Such a struggle finds legitimacy in the fact that certain groups have suffered prejudice and discrimination for centuries, such as blacks and people with disabilities.

Due to the stigma that marks these people, the struggle for recognition of their rights becomes legitimate. Currently, even at the institutional level, there is a movement on the part

of legislators so that the so-called minorities have their human rights to employment, education, culture and all areas of society guaranteed. Recently, public policies have emerged in order to expand the number of companies, as is the case of law 8213/91²⁶, which guarantees people with any type of disability, whether visible or not, the right to employment.

This right is expressed in article 93, which says that companies with 100 (one hundred) employees must reserve 2 to 5% of their positions for rehabilitated or disabled beneficiaries. This law is quite broad and deals with the purpose and principles of social security and represented an enormous advance in the sense of giving this part of the population access to the fundamental right to work, which is guaranteed in the Federal Constitution in its Art. 170. This right is considered one of the most important of all fundamental rights and is what underlies the economic order. (Federal Constitution of 1998)²⁷

Thanks to this law, people with the most diverse types of disabilities had the opportunity to have a job, to be able to support themselves and their families. We know that the law alone is not capable of solving a social issue that has existed for centuries and involves other issues such as mistaken beliefs and a culture focused on exclusion, but it was the lever that led companies to hire people with disabilities. The presence of these people has transformed Organizations into a place where there is diversity, making it more open to people who escape a standard of normality. Disabled people had the opportunity to show their ability to work despite their disabilities.

At the international level, there are several regulatory frameworks such as the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UN, 1948), proclaimed in the city of Paris on December 10, 1948 by the United Nations General Assembly. It was the first time that universal protection of human rights was established. This declaration is considered the framework from which other international laws emerged, such as the International Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities. Our country participated intensely in the debates that gave rise to the text of the convention, and people with disabilities also had the opportunity to participate. This Convention was incorporated in 2009 and our country is one of several signatory countries to this convention.

More recently, we had the publication in 2015 of the Federal Statute known as LBI – Brazilian Inclusion Law. (Law 13,146, 2015). This law, however, is better known as the

²⁶It provides in its Art. 93 that a company with 100 (one hundred) or more employees is obliged to fill from 2% (two percent) to 5% (five percent) of its positions with rehabilitated beneficiaries or qualified persons with disabilities.

²⁷In its article 170, it states that the economic order, founded on the valorization of human work and free initiative, aims to ensure a dignified existence for all, in accordance with the dictates of social justice.

Statute of Persons with Disabilities. Thus, we can see that from Greece where people who were born with disabilities were thrown off cliffs to the present day there has been an immense advance. It is known, however, that much needs to be done to include these people in the most diverse sectors of society. Currently, there is also a greater openness within the Organizations to welcome people with different sexual orientations.

This debate has been taking place in different spaces and the issue of gender identity and heteronormativity has been debated as an outdated posture in the face of human diversity also in the matter of human sexuality. Such a debate has been taking place even in the legislature that has been omitted for a long time when the issue is gender identity. It is known that for centuries transsexuals, homosexuals, transvestites and transgender people have lived on the margins of society, suffering discrimination and violence of the most diverse types and many have lost their lives due to prejudice. With such a scenario, principles such as human dignity, freedom and equality have been disrespected, striking the Federal Constitution itself, which says that everyone is equal before the law.

In the legislative scope, we can mention the Bill 5.002 of 2013, which provides for the right to gender identity, authored by Jean Wyllys. This project has been archived since 2019 based on art. 105 of the internal regulations of the Chamber of Deputies. It is necessary to understand diversity as a natural aspect of human nature, where ethnic, cultural, generational, religious and other diversity must be welcomed in order to have a peaceful and harmonious coexistence that enriches society. Here, on the topic of diversity within organizations, we can understand that it enriches the environment, expands the range of views about the business itself and, therefore, is a factor of competitive advantage within organizations.

2 DIVERSITY SEEN AS A COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGE

Nowadays, a concept called alterity is often used. What does alterity mean? According to the online dictionary of Portuguese means ' Character or state of what is different, distinct, what is another. Which is opposed to identity, to what is proper and particular; who sees the other as a distinct, different being. ' (Online Dictionary, 2021).

Alterity derives from the Latin *alteritas* which means 'other', this concept raises the question of difference, that is, the other is the one who is distinguished from me, that is, the other is not equal to me, he is not my mirror, he has its own characteristics. It is a very important concept widely used in the social sciences. Alterity is the condition of being the

other, different from me and here when the word different is used, it refers to the most varied aspects, whether physical, cultural, etc.

Thus, since alterity is the condition of being different (*alter*) and we all differ even minimally from each other and not even identical twins who have the same genetic load are the same, since each one has a distinct personality, it follows that a another concept is interconnected here. Which would be? This is the concept of empathy. Empathy can be understood as the ability to put oneself, let's say, 'in the place' of the other, 'put on the other's shoe'. It is the ability to care about the well-being of other people. Such capacity requires sensitivity to look at and accept the other with their own characteristics in an attitude of respect and consideration for the other, the one who differs from me being neither better nor worse, just alter, diverse. Alterity, therefore, relates to the concept of identity.

Thus, it is only possible to recognize that someone is disabled in relation to someone who is not disabled. **Identity** is formed from the difference between one and the other . To think about otherness, therefore, is to think about infinite ways of living, of believing, of being in the world. If companies are formed by individuals in society and society is diverse, how could we think of organizations composed only of certain types of people?

It is not organizations that form society, but society that forms companies. In a society there are the most diverse types of people who are distinguished by their beliefs, by their values, by their physical characteristics, by their sexual orientations and many other characteristics. Thus, people management within Organizations must rethink its practices by developing programs capable of transforming organizations into environments capable of dealing with the issue of human diversity.

The objective is to bring social justice as all people can have opportunities regardless of their characteristics. Companies thus start to act in the sense of human solidarity where in their staff there are disabled people, blacks, women, people over 40 years old, people with different sexual orientations, etc. Such an organization can then make use of this diversity in order to leverage its own business. A diverse environment tends to be a storehouse of innovative ideas capable of making the company grow in the financial aspect.

Thinking of a diverse organization as opposed to seeming an act of mere kindness on the part of Organizations is a movement that leads to a better strategy on the part of companies or Organizations. Organizations that are proposing to this challenge will have to learn to deal with this issue of diversity, that is, to deal with those who deviate from the dominant pattern.

Groups such as blacks for example are a minority within the Organizations and this is due to structural racism. A study carried out by the IBGE showed that in the 3rd quarter of 2019, 65.2% of the unemployed were black and brown, with whites representing 34% (IBGE, 2019). It is only possible to understand this immense inequality of opportunities by understanding that racism in Brazil is structural. This is the understanding of several authors, several scholars and also the professor of law at the USP law school Eunice Prudente in an interview given to USP radio on July 31, 2020. According to her, black women suffer from triple discrimination for being a woman, for being black and poor. It reports that according to *'according to IBGE data, 54% of the population is black and that, according to Data from Ipea – Institute of Applied Economic Research, 2016, it shows that white women receive 70% more than black women'*. The teacher makes clear in her interview the complexity of the topic, saying that it is necessary to study the topic in an intersectional way, approaching the tripod gender-ethnicity-social class. She remembered important dates such as the International Day of Black, Latino and Caribbean Women (25/07/1992).

The issue of gender when studying black women needs to take into account a slave mentality that lasted three centuries, yes, 300 years. And Angela Davis in her most important work argues that black people were seen as property without taking into account the issue of gender. Women were simply a tool of work, they were not seen as women. They performed the same functions as men, such as heavy farm work. (Davis, 2016).

We can infer that one of the reasons why black women are left out of the feminist struggle to guarantee their rights is this rancidity of slavery that still remains alive in our social fabric, whether consciously or unconsciously, through unfounded beliefs that exclude, that humiliate and marginalize the black people despite being the majority of the population. It is a nation that denies itself, denies its essence, denies its origin, denies its own characteristics, denies its culture, denies its own history, its Afro-descendants. Thus, when it comes to access to work, the situation of women is even worse than that of men.

In an article published on March 4 of this year, a study by the IBGE was published, which revealed that in 2019 there were 54.5% of women aged 15 years and over were part of the workforce, while for men the percentage was 73.7%. Already *'an additional difficulty for insertion in the market can be observed in the racial cut of the data. Black or brown women with children up to 3 years old had the lowest levels of occupation. 'less than 50%, while white women registered a percentage of 62.6%' (IBGE, 2019).*

Silvio Luiz de Almeida, in his book *What is structural racism?*, says that racism “is a systematic form of discrimination based on race, and which is manifested through conscious or unconscious practices that culminate in disadvantages or privileges, depending on the racial group to which they belong” (Almeida, 2018). Slavery in Brazil lasted from 1550 to 1888, that is, there were 300 years of slavery and Brazilian society still perceives blacks as inferior people because of their race, a very sad fact in the 21st century. It is necessary that the managers of Brazilian companies are aware that there is a historical debt to this portion of the Brazilian population, which represents 54% of the country's population.

It is necessary to give these people the opportunity to work because to hire them is to make organizations a diverse, plural environment that includes everyone. It is high time to practice inclusion within organizations in an effective way because companies have a social responsibility towards society for generating wealth, goods aimed at a consumer society. Therefore, everyone needs to have access to the goods that are produced through their work, it is not a favor, but the realization of a right guaranteed in the Federal Constitution. The lack of opportunity to access employment puts people on the margins of society and companies are responsible for this insofar as they leave this part of the population out of their staff.

3. THE ADVANTAGES OF THE PRACTICE OF INCLUDING THE DIVERSITY OF COMPANIES

In 2019, Brazil ranked 7th in the Kantar inclusion index ²⁸, the first global inclusion and diversity index with more than 14 countries. The country was next to countries like Mexico and Singapore in the discrimination index, which requires effective action on the part of organizations in order to change this scenario. A report published by the McKinsey consultancy showed that there is a 35% increase in company profits when there is diversity.

Latin American companies that embrace diversity tend to outperform other companies in key business practices like innovation and collaboration, and their leaders are better at fostering trust and teamwork. They also tend to

²⁸The Kantar Inclusion Index reveals how diversity and inclusion rates differ globally. Canada tops the leader board when it comes to the most inclusive and diverse country in which to work, this is driven by good gender representations (over 40% female) at senior levels; and 65% of Canadians believing their companies are actively trying to be more inclusive and diverse and supportive of all employees, regardless of who they are. On the downside, 20% of Canadians reported experiencing bullying in the past year. The USA comes a close second, with the drivers here being equal gender representation at senior leadership level, and 30% representation at senior leadership in terms of ethnicity; 63% of Americans believe their company is actively trying to be more inclusive and diverse and 67% believe their company supports all employees, regardless of who they are. But, despite this rosy picture, 17% of Americans said they had experienced bullying in the past year. Brazil, Mexico and Singapore were the countries found to have the highest levels of workplace bullying. Italy, Netherlands and Spain were the countries found to have the lowest levels of bullying.

have happier work environments and better talent retention. All of this translates into both stronger organizational health and results: companies that embrace diversity are significantly more likely to outperform their peers that do not. (The Kantar Index 2019).

These findings come from an extensive McKinsey & Company study of the state of corporate diversity in Latin America. The study draws on four main sources:

- A dataset of nearly 700 publicly traded companies covering all major industries headquartered in Brazil, Chile, Peru, Argentina, Colombia and Panama. This data was filtered from a larger sample to ensure that only companies with complete financial and gender data were included in the analyzed dataset.
- An extensive survey of 3,900 employees at various levels from more than 1,300 of the largest companies in the region, creating a holistic understanding of diversity from an employee perspective. The companies included in the survey had more than 500 employees.
- The Organizational Health Index (OHI), a proprietary McKinsey database based on surveys of nearly 60,000 employees at 40 companies in Latin America, as well as our global dataset of 5 million surveys in 100 countries.
- In-depth interviews with more than 30 senior executives from leading companies in Latin America.

This study is exploratory and seeks to establish connections between issues of gender, race/ethnicity and sexual orientation, establishing a relationship between the issue of diversity, organizational health and the issue of performance. The study makes it clear that this is not a causal relationship, however, there is a link between diversity and performance. The study demonstrates that companies committed to the issue of human diversity generate in people a positive perception that tends to bring positive results to it. Despite this, minority groups and women still remain underrepresented in leadership positions in Latin America. This means that Organizations must develop policies and programs aimed at providing opportunities for these groups. As already said, it is a matter of social justice and companies have a huge responsibility in this since they produce goods and services, that is, wealth and this wealth should not be shared only with certain groups, but with the whole of society. . Companies or organizations represent society, they are formed in the social body and, as they discriminate against certain groups, they are also responsible for the situation of marginality in which they live.

There are studies that show that the vast majority of the black population lives far from urban centers, living on the outskirts and slums of cities in this country. This reality has to do with the occupation of urban land by former slaves, as well.

Shops, basements, tenements, shacks built on the outskirts of the city then became alternatives found by the slave to build a living space for himself, independent of the master's control. [...] In addition, the gain gave the captive the possibility of managing their own time and rhythm of work, also allowing the regrouping of those who had the same ethnic and cultural origins. (Gomes, 1990).

In this way, to change this scenario where the black population of the country has less access to employment, housing, education, it is necessary to break the cycle of exclusion, but without the collaboration of those who generate the country's wealth, which are small, medium and large companies, the ideal of equality remains what it is, an ideal. It is necessary to materialize the ideal of justice, the ideal of equality, the principle of human dignity. If the struggle exists, it is because we believe in it and on the path towards social justice there have already been gains, there have already been countless victories although the journey is long.

Each person who had the opportunity to access a job represents a victory not for the law, but for justice, because the law is just an instrument for the realization of rights. A good law is one that 'takes', as they say, that reaches people's hearts, that meets people's desires and makes them engage and implement them through policies, programs and actions that generate opportunities. It is necessary to understand that there is no magic, what exists is joint work, conscious work of education, clarification, information for people in society, a work of sensitization that makes a human being look at the other and recognize him as your equal not in the skin, not in the beliefs, not in the values, but in what equals us that is our human nature. Thus, when each one, in a gesture of empathy, puts himself in the other's place, he will want to include him and not the other way around.

Research such as this one demonstrates that welcoming diversity is advantageous for Organizations as it makes the work environment healthier, happier, enables the exchange of different experiences, which enriches the work environment and enables better performance that translates into profit. for companies.

There are companies in Brazil that invest heavily in inclusion programs. According to the 2020 Guia Exame, the Sabin laboratory has 75% of women on its staff and 55% of blacks, with blacks occupying half of the positions in leadership positions. The company has 5,765 employees and fulfills the quota for hiring people with disabilities, which in this case is 5% in

accordance with article 93 of law 8,213/91. It also has inclusion programs for the LGBTI+ group. Diversity inclusion practices, in addition to improving the image of companies before society as a whole, also generate a huge competitive advantage in relation to those companies that do not have inclusion programs, as employees work with much more commitment in a company that in fact recognizes the potential and really provides opportunity for people regardless of their race, religion, age, physical condition, etc. If the person is prepared for the role, why not welcome him and give him the ability to improve his life through his own work? This is the opinion of Lídia Abdalla, president of the Sabin diagnostic medicine laboratory. The Laboratory was classified as company of the year by the second edition of the Exame Diversity Guide 2020. (Exame Diversity Guide, 2020).

Companies that have their human resources, which are people valued in a vision of plurality, that respect the other for what he is, have a highly positive image in society and thus attract greater and better investments. Currently, there is a movement in all sectors of society towards the inclusion of stigmatized minorities who have been kept on the margins of society for centuries, such as people with disabilities, blacks, women and those with a sexual orientation that is outside the standard of heteronormativity.

Companies that have an intelligent and visionary management have already realized that the theme of inclusion is on the agenda on social networks, on TV, on the radio, including in the legislature with proposals as we saw as the PL 5002/2013 authored by Jean Wyllys that has on the right to gender identity. Thus, it is noted that this movement did not affect a particular sector, but all sectors of society, the discussion is on everyone's lips and companies that do not adhere to this new reality will be left behind, will lose competitiveness. In the past people with a different sexual orientation from what is known as heteronormativity hid 'in the closet', today people come out and want to be accepted. It is as if the Constitution itself were screaming in our ears: everyone is equal before the law without distinction of any kind. It is a formal right taking shape, materializing into something alive, real, present in the world of men and not only in the cold letter of the law.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

This article aims to discuss diversity within organizations as a factor of competitive advantage. We have seen that there is a society-wide movement that began in 1948 with the Universal Declaration of Human Rights that recognized the inherent dignity of all members of the human family and the equal rights of men and women. That established in its art.I that all

people are born free and equal in dignity and Rights and that in its art.VII it recognized that “all are equal before the law and are entitled, without any distinction, to the equal protection of the law. All are entitled to equal protection against any discrimination in violation of this Declaration”. (UN, 1948).

We saw that this declaration was the framework for the emergence of numerous other legal instruments such as the International Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, which entered our legal system through Decree 6.949/2009.

Through a bibliographic survey, we saw that there is a movement from different sectors of society such as the feminist movements for women's rights, the LGBTQI+ movement, the movement of people with disabilities, the movement of black people. We could see that little by little the whole society is welcoming human diversity and that includes companies. Studies have shown that companies that have given opportunities to discriminated groups in society such as blacks, people with disabilities, women and people with a different sexual orientation from heteronormativity have several gains such as improving the company's image, a healthy work environment, with motivated and engaged people and this brings a competitive advantage that translates into profit for these companies. Finally, it is necessary to say that inclusion is a strategic behavior and companies that do not want to join this movement that is not from Brazil but a global movement will lose competitiveness in the market and be left behind in terms of profitability for their partners. It is high time that society as a whole respect its Federal Constitution which says that all are equal before the law without distinction of any kind, as established in the Federal Constitution of 1988 in its Article 5. And the right to work is a social right expressed in art.6 of our Magna Carta.

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